

EDUCATION AND EDUCATION IN PRIMARY CLASSES INTEGRATION

Jamoldinova Fotimaxon Xusanboy qizi

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the innovative integration of education and upbringing in primary classes.

In the next four years, a number of reforms are being carried out in our republic in order to educate the young generation in the spirit of patriotism and provide education based on modern information technologies. In the process of globalization, the attention and demand for introducing interactive methods and innovative technologies in education is increasing.

In his speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the Day of Teachers and Trainers, the honorable President said, "It is clear to all of us that the cornerstone of development and the force that makes the country powerful and the nation great is science, education and training. The bright future of our country, first of all, is the education system and They paid special attention to the fact that it is closely related to the education we give to our children.

After all, a child's worldview, taste, interests, and love of knowledge are formed in primary grades. Accordingly, in the educational process, only the establishment of a conscious discipline, characteristic of the cooperation between the teacher and the students, leads to the further improvement and improvement of the environment of teaching the student to acquire knowledge and independent thinking.

It is appropriate for a modern primary school teacher to strictly adhere to the following principles, which are considered the characteristics of the modern teaching method, in the effective course of his professional activity and adaptation:

1. Programming (planning) of the educational process according to scientific and ideological principles;
2. Adaptation of the level of complexity of educational material and the pace of learning to the age and individual psychological characteristics of students;
3. To ensure that students' theoretical and practical training are interconnected and integrated;

4. Increasing student activity and modernity of the educational process;
5. Conducting individual-practical and collective work of students;
6. Acceleration of the educational process with the help of modern technical tools and many technology modes;
7. Differentiation of education and the complex of academic subjects - in the latest projects of computer programs

In order to harmonize the process of education and upbringing, the primary school teacher must follow the following principles:

a) the principle of self-management follows the rules of regular formation and improvement of the effective organization of educational and cognitive activities;

b) the principle of evolution implies constant changes and renewal of the forms and methods of the educational-psychological process;

v) the principle of autonomy - directs the teacher and the pupil to perform initiative and active dynamic actions in the educational process;

g) the principle of responsibility - it requires consistent monitoring of the actions and behaviors performed by oneself in acquiring knowledge, qualifications and skills;

d) the principle of role participation - it requires the teacher and the learner to perform separate professional functions: the teacher organizes the educational activity of the student - the manager; and the student plays the role of executor;

e) the principle of ensuring psychological quality and efficiency - this implies that all components of teacher's and students' activities are coordinated as a single mechanism;

It shows that all members of the team help each other to achieve a common goal, strive to overcome difficulties together, and show their moral and spiritual cooperation.

Pedagogical and psychological scientists say that the most important qualities of a modern school teacher should consist of the following:

1. The teacher's personal qualities: loyalty to his homeland, people, love of children, practical and psychological literacy, hard work and creativity, active in public affairs, love of books, kindness, humanity, humility, nobility, sincerity, determination, boldness and strong character, striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills.

2. Knowledge of the teacher's profession: deep understanding of the essence of the education and training process, understanding of its goals and tasks, mastering the

knowledge bases of general psychology, pedagogical and youth psychology, ethnopsychology, knowledge of the theoretical and practical foundations of modern pedagogy, and mastering the methodology of teaching one's subject, to understand the cognitive processes and psychological characteristics of elementary school children, to know the effective methods of educational influence on them, to understand the essence of the educational work carried out with parents and the public.

3. Qualities specific to the teacher's profession: understanding the national idea and national spirituality, and being loyal to it, understanding the importance of universal and national wealth, traditions, values and customs that form the basis of modern education and training, pedagogical skills that ensure the quality and effectiveness of the teacher's work, mutual manifestation of such components as pedagogical observation, the ability to properly distribute one's attention, the development of pedagogical fantasy, critical attitude to oneself, self-control, the presence of pedagogical tact and emotional expression of speech are of great importance.

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